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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ
ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE**UKTAMOVA Yulduzkhon Umarovna**
KHUDOYAROVA Dildora RakhimovnaDSc, professor
Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan**IDENTIFICATION OF RISK FACTORS AND PATHOGENESIS OF PREECLAMPSIA
(LITERATURE REVIEW)**

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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17087558>**ABSTRACT**

Preeclampsia is a formidable disease that occurs in women after the 20th week of pregnancy and is accompanied by a triad of symptoms. These symptoms include edema, increased blood pressure and proteinuria. Untimely diagnosis of this pathology can lead to HELLP syndrome H – hemolysis, EL – elevated liver enzymes, LP – low level platelet (thrombocytopenia). It in turn can lead to maternal mortality. Further therapy is aimed at preventing liver complications in preeclampsia.

Keywords: preeclampsia, HELLP syndrome, liver manifestations, pregnancy

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**ВЫЯВЛЕНИЕ ФАКТОРОВ РИСКА И ПАТОГЕНЕЗ ПРЕЭКЛАМПСИИ (ОБЗОР
ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Преэклампсия — грозное заболевание, которое возникает у женщин после 20-й недели беременности и сопровождается триадой симптомов. К этим симптомам относятся отеки, повышение артериального давления и протеинурия. Несвоевременная диагностика данной патологии может привести к HELLP-синдрому (H – hemolysis (гемолиз), EL – elevated liver enzymes (повышение активности печеночных ферментов), LP – low level platelet (тромбоцитопения)). Он в свою очередь может привести к материнской смертности. По данным литератур, было выявлено, что существует негласная классификация преэклампсии, которая включает в себя раннюю и позднюю преэклампсии, что соответствует манифестации данной патологии до 34 и после 34 недель гестации. Дальнейшая терапия направлена на

профилактику печеночных осложнений при преэклампсии. Профилактика, в свою очередь направлена на выявление групп риска, разделение их на группы высокого и низкого риска, а также определение эпидемиологического статуса пациентов, имеющих преэклампсию в анамнезе. В данной обзорной статье будут рассмотрены результаты мета-анализов и будут сравниваться между собой.

Ключевые слова: преэклампсия, HELLP-синдром, печеночные проявления, беременность

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PREKLAMPSIYA XAVF OMILLARI VA PATOGENEZINI ANIQLASH (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

ANNOTATSIYA

Preeklampsiya - bu homiladorlikning 20-haftasidan keyin ayollarda paydo bo'ladigan va simptomlar triadasi bilan birga keladigan daxshatli kasallikdir. Ushbu alomatlar shish, qon bosimi ortishi va proteinuriyani o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu patologiyaning o'z vaqtida tashxislash HELLP sindromiga (H - gemoliz, EL - jigar fermentlarining ko'tarilishi, LP - past darajadagi trombositlar (trombositopeniya) olib kelishi mumkin. Bu o'z navbatida onalar o'limiga olib kelishi mumkin. Keyingi terapiya preeklampsida jigar asoratlarining oldini olishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: preeklampsiya, HELLP sindromi, jigardagi o'zgarishlar, homiladorlik

Introduction

Preeclampsia accounts for 2-8% of all pregnancies. This pathology significantly increases maternal and child mortality. It negatively affects vital organs such as the liver, kidneys, brain, and lungs. Even though the pathogenesis is not fully understood, 40 theories are presented, which are not recommended to be considered separately. In Russian sources, it is customary to distinguish between early and late preeclampsia, based on the time of manifestation of clinical symptoms. [16] The formation of early preeclampsia up to 34 weeks is based on placental causes associated with impaired restructuring of the spiral arteries during trophoblast invasion. As a result, nutrition and blood supply to the placenta decreases, which can soon lead to placental ischemia. As for late preeclampsia, it is mainly associated with extragenital pathology or previous chronic diseases, such as chronic arterial hypertension, metabolic syndrome, and diabetes mellitus. In turn, foreign literature suggests considering the most extensive division of preeclampsia into premature preeclampsia, developing at a period of up to 32 weeks, and timely, developing at a period of 32 to 37 weeks. [6]. Most of the identified risk factors are based on the severity of proteinuria, edema, and diastolic pressure. However, the clinical picture of other somatic pathologies not associated with pregnancy is completely or partially ignored. They, in turn, are of great importance since they contribute to the development of systemic multiorgan reactions.

Materials and research methods

We studied the literature of Russian and foreign authors and conducted a comparative analysis of their approaches to the study of risk factors and pathogenesis of preeclampsia.

Results and their discussion

There is a distribution by risk groups that help to rationally introduce pregnancy in women who deserve attention. According to Chang KJ, Seow KM, Chen KH. Preeclampsia: Recent Advances in Predicting, Preventing, and Managing the Maternal and Fetal Life-Threatening Condition. 2023, factors preeclampsia can be divided into high-risk and moderate-risk factors, as well as factors that are still being studied.[4]

Based on this data, we have developed a table 1.

Table 1

Risk factors for preeclampsia and their causes.

Risk factor	
History of preeclampsia	Pre-eclampsia in previous pregnancies. The earlier pre-eclampsia developed the previous time and the more severe it was, the higher the risk of recurrence.
Multiple pregnancy	Pregnancy with twins, triplets, etc. significantly increases the risk of preeclampsia due to the increased stress on the body.
Chronic hypertension	Arterial hypertension that existed before pregnancy. High blood pressure negatively affects the condition of blood vessels, including the placenta.
Diabetes mellitus type 1 or 2	Diabetes, especially if poorly controlled, increases the risk of preeclampsia. High blood sugar damages blood vessels.
Kidney diseases	Chronic kidney disease, such as glomerulonephritis or pyelonephritis, increases the risk of preeclampsia.
Autoimmune diseases	Some autoimmune diseases, such as antiphospholipid syndrome (APS) and systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), are associated with an increased risk of preeclampsia.
Obesity (BMI > 30)	Being overweight or obese is a risk factor for many pregnancy complications, including preeclampsia.

Other risk factors that may increase your risk of preeclampsia include:

First pregnancy: Women who have had their first pregnancy have a slightly higher risk of preeclampsia than women who have had more than one. This is because the woman’s body is experiencing pregnancy-related changes for the first time and may be more sensitive to them. **Age over 35:** The risk of preeclampsia increases with age, especially in women over 35. This may be due to age-related changes in blood vessels, which become less elastic and more susceptible to damage, as well as an increase in the incidence of chronic diseases in older women. **Family history:** Having a mother or sister with preeclampsia also increases a woman’s risk of developing the condition. This may indicate a genetic predisposition to preeclampsia, although the specific genes responsible have not yet been identified. **The interval between pregnancies of more than 10 years:** Having a long gap between pregnancies may also increase the risk of preeclampsia. It is believed that over a long period, a woman's body can "forget" the state of pregnancy, and therefore the first pregnancy after a long break can proceed with an increased risk of complications.

In addition to the above risk factors, the article by Chang KJ, Seow KM, Chen KH mentions other factors whose association with preeclampsia requires further study. These include: race and ethnicity and smoking. Some studies suggest that women of African descent have a higher risk of preeclampsia than women of other races. However, this may be due not only to genetic factors, but also to socioeconomic conditions, access to health care, and other factors. Smoking during pregnancy is a risk factor for many complications, including preeclampsia. However, the relationship between smoking and preeclampsia is not as clear-cut as with other complications. Some studies suggest that smoking may even reduce the risk of preeclampsia, but this may be because women who smoke are more likely to have other risk factors, such as low birth weight and premature birth, which may mask the effect of smoking on the development of preeclampsia.

Perry et al., 2022 offer a slightly different formula for determining risk groups. It includes, along with the above factors, also dietary errors made by women in the pre-gestational and gestational periods.

According to their study, which included 2,404 women in the UK, women in the main group who consumed 1,000 mg of vitamin C showed no benefit in preventing pre-eclampsia, and no difference in the groups with severe pre-eclampsia. In a controlled study by Williams et al [20] there were 2 groups, of which 22 were in the main group with preeclampsia and 40 women in the control group. Quantitative analysis of fatty acids was studied, it was found that women with lower fatty acid values were 7.6 times more likely to develop preeclampsia and were at risk.

Vitamin D may have protective properties because it ensures proper implantation of the trophoblast. Numerous studies have shown that women with vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy have a higher risk of developing preeclampsia than women with sufficient levels of this vitamin. Vitamin D has immunomodulatory properties, meaning it affects the functioning of the immune system. It is believed that an imbalance in the immune system may play a role in the development of preeclampsia. Sufficient levels of vitamin D can help maintain normal immune function during pregnancy and reduce the risk of preeclampsia. Vitamin D plays an important role in regulating the function of the placenta, which provides nutrition and oxygen to the fetus. Vitamin D deficiency can lead to impaired development and functioning of the placenta, which can contribute to the development of preeclampsia. Vitamin D can affect the regulation of blood pressure. Vitamin D deficiency can contribute to high blood pressure, which is one of the main signs of preeclampsia. Also, its deficiency is associated with endothelial dysfunction, which is a pathogenetic link in preeclampsia. [7]

Calcium plays a critical role during pregnancy, participating in the formation of the fetal skeleton, regulation of muscle function, transmission of nerve impulses, and blood clotting. Calcium plays an important role in regulating the function of the placenta, which provides the fetus with nutrients and oxygen. Calcium deficiency can lead to impaired development and functioning of the placenta, which can contribute to the development of preeclampsia. Calcium is involved in the regulation of blood pressure. Sufficient calcium intake helps maintain normal blood pressure during pregnancy, which reduces the risk of preeclampsia. It is emphasized that "calcium deficiency during pregnancy is associated with an increased risk of preeclampsia." Numerous studies confirm this relationship, showing that women with insufficient calcium intake have a higher risk of preeclampsia. [5,14]

The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends calcium supplements during pregnancy to prevent preeclampsia, especially in areas with low calcium intake.

A major role in predicting preeclampsia is played by liver biomarkers alanine aminotransferase and aspartate aminotransferase [12]) sought to find out whether levels of certain liver biomarkers in the first trimester of pregnancy (up to 14 weeks) can predict the development of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, such as preeclampsia, gestational hypertension, and others. This was a prospective cohort study. Pregnant women who measured the levels of alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase, alkaline phosphatase and calculated the liver steatosis index (LSI) in the first trimester. Then, the development of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was observed during pregnancy. The association between biomarker levels and the risk of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was statistically analyzed. The results of the study revealed that elevated levels of gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase, alkaline phosphatase, and ISF in the first trimester are associated with an increased risk of developing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. The strongest association with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was found for gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase, alkaline phosphatase, and ISF. Alanine aminotransferase levels and the aspartate aminotransferase/alanine aminotransferase ratio did not show a significant association with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. These associations remained even after adjusting for other risk factors such as age, BMI, parity (number of births), and the presence of chronic diseases. Importantly, the association with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was also maintained in the subgroup of women with normal BMI (maternal body mass index). The results of

the study suggest that measuring gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase, gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase and ISF levels in the first trimester of pregnancy may be useful in identifying women at increased risk of developing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. These biomarkers may help in early diagnosis and timely initiation of preventive measures to reduce the risk of complications associated with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. Significance of the study: The study highlights the importance of early assessment of risk factors for hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and offers a new approach to predicting this complication using available liver biomarkers. This may contribute to improving pregnancy outcomes for the mother and child.

Certain dietary supplements, such as calcium, vitamin D, omega-3 fatty acids, antioxidants and L-arginine, may have a positive effect on vascular function in pregnant women with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, including preeclampsia.

Pathogenesis of preeclampsia

In the last ten years, our understanding of the pathogenesis of preeclampsia has progressively changed. It has been suggested that early and late preeclampsia differ in pathophysiology. Early preeclampsia is diagnosed before 34 weeks of gestation. Late after 34 weeks of pregnancy. It should be understood that if the mother of the pregnant woman has a predisposition to cardiovascular pathologies, the likelihood of preeclampsia also increases. Pathology in early preeclampsia begins with abnormal formation of blood vessels in the maternal uterine spiral arteries. Late manifestation is also called maternal preeclampsia, in which there is a decrease in arterial conversion and placental perfusion. These changes in the spiral arteries, namely low flow pressure to the placenta, are necessary for fetal nutrition.

According to Khodjaev Z.S., Kogan E.A. and others, the placental site was studied and a significant decrease in the depth of the trophoblast and extravillous trophoblast cells in women with preeclampsia was revealed compared to the main group. The shape and size of the remodeled spiral arteries coincide with the data from the studied literature. They had a wide lumen, thin and fragile walls, and were also characterized by the absence of smooth muscle cells. Arteries that were not subject to remodeling were characterized by hypertrophied sclerotic walls, a narrow lumen, and some had foci of necrosis, hemorrhage, and microthrombosis. Morphologically altered walls prevent normal trophoblast ingrowth and subsequently impair the functioning of the placenta during the entire gestational process.

In turn, Lipatov I.S., Tezikov Yu.V. and others put forward a theory of the influence of metabolic processes on the acceleration of preeclampsia. Their study examined 50 women with preeclampsia against the background of metabolic syndrome, 32 women without clinically confirmed metabolic syndrome. The results of their studies show the similarity of preeclampsia with metabolic syndrome and insulin resistance. In a detailed blood test and biochemical analysis, similarities in manifestations were revealed, such as hyperinsulinemia, leptinemia, thrombotic inflammatory status, visceral type of fat deposition, hyperuricemia. This proves that the metabolic link plays an important role in the development of preeclampsia. [11]

Kaptilny V.A., Reyshtat D.Yu. consider the pathogenesis of preeclampsia in a two-stage theory. Physiologically, during pregnancy, it is characterized by two waves of trophoblast invasion into the spiral arteries. The first wave is considered complete when trophoblast invasion occurs in the endometrial segment of the spiral arteries, and the second, when the myometrial segment is affected. In preeclampsia, stage 1 of the theory is that invasion of the myometrial segment does not occur completely, which leads to placental ischemia. The second stage begins with the ischemic placenta beginning to produce antiangiogenic factors in the maternal bloodstream. This in turn leads to endothelial dysfunction. Endothelial dysfunction has several features, including impaired production of endothelial relaxing factors, such as nitric oxide and endothelin I. Their decrease leads to a decrease in vascular reactivity, vasoconstriction develops, the glomerular filtration rate decreases and this leads to a violation of the hemostasis systems and intravascular coagulation.[8]

Lipatov I.S. and others consider another theory of the pathogenesis of preeclampsia, which has an immune nature. It is believed that the pathogenesis is based on an imbalance between pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory factors. Physiological pregnancy proceeds in such a way that the mother develops immunity to a foreign agent in the form of a fetus since tolerance to the fetus is created. In preeclampsia, this balance is disturbed and the formation of pro-inflammatory factors prevails. Predictors of the immune response during pregnancy are T lymphocytes or rather their imbalance. T helpers of the first type are pro-inflammatory, while T helpers of the second type are anti-inflammatory. As stated above, T helpers of the first type increase. The theory of an autoimmune response to placental and vascular endothelial cells is also confirmed. During pregnancy, the production of proinflammatory enzymes also increases due to an increase in cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and interleukin-17 (IL-17). [2]

Diagram 1. Stage of preeclampsia development

Conclusions

Identification of risk groups has expanded significantly over the past 10 years. To select women who are at risk, it is necessary to conduct a thorough collection of anamnesis, and complaints, and study

the clinical tests of the pregnant woman. This will help identify women who are at risk and take measures recommended by WHO, including calcium supplementation, L-arginine, vitamin D, and low-dose aspirin daily. It has been proven that an integrated approach to this pathology can significantly reduce risks and improve perinatal and maternal outcomes.

Despite advanced technologies in obstetrics, a single theory on the pathogenesis of preeclampsia has not been approved. Many scientists point to the multifactorial and polyetiological nature of the disease. This is proven by the above studies. However, what scientists agree on is that the placental and immune role in the development of preeclampsia plays a key role, since it is with it that the chain of biochemical reactions begins, which leads to immune responses and endothelial dysfunction. No less important role has also been shown by the direct and inverse relationship between metabolic syndrome and diabetic-like conditions on the development of this hypertensive disorder.

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